

Outer Space
Institute Report

**Astronomy and the Proliferation of Space Objects:
Strategies for Addressing Orbital Light and Spectrum
Pollution**

Astronomy and the Proliferation of Space Objects: Strategies for Addressing Orbital Light and Spectrum Pollution

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This report is a public version of a discussion paper prepared for the Astro-Sat Workshop held in Vancouver, November 2023. Workshop participants included members of the International Astronomical Union’s (IAU) Center for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky (CPS), and of the CPS Work Package 2 (WP2), as well as other experts from multiple disciplines and backgrounds.

Although this report is independent from CPS, some sections were prompted, in part, by the work of the WP2 team. Further details about the CPS WP2 team and its output can be found at the IAU CPS website: <https://cps.iau.org/>

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Cover image by Rolando Ligustri. A 20-minute exposure of comet C/2023 A3 (Tsuchinshan-ATLAS), with approximately two dozen satellite streaks.

The new celestial sphere

Top: The Yale Bright Star catalogue projected onto the celestial sphere. The catalogue includes 9,110 objects, almost all of which are stars with V magnitudes brighter than 6.5 mag. The catalogue represents approximately every star that can be seen with the unaided eye under dark sky conditions. Bottom: All satellites and rocket bodies on orbit as of 23 August 2023. The catalogue is projected onto the celestial sphere, so it is a hypothetical view of the entire sky, similar to that shown for the top panel. North is up and east is to the left.

A moment of satellites

Two instantaneous views of satellites in the sky using only the current satellites and rocket bodies in orbit. The coordinates show azimuth and altitude, with the outer circle representing the horizon and each concentric ring representing 10° altitude. Top panel: The view from La Palma, Spain at the specified time. Bottom panel: A view from the Dominion Astronomical Observatory in Victoria, BC. The band shown across the sky in both plots is the geosynchronous region. Not all objects shown will be observable. However, they are also moving on the order of a degree per second, creating a continuously changing sky view with a large fraction of the sky being cross-cut by a satellite every tens of seconds.

Introduction

The recent, rapid proliferation of space objects, especially “megaconstellations” composed of hundreds, thousands, or even tens of thousands of satellites, is threatening both optical and radio astronomy. This has caused astronomers to come together to identify, and then pursue, changes to industry practices as well as domestic and international policies and laws.

The purpose of the ASTRO-SAT workshop – held in Vancouver, Canada, in November 2023 – was to develop strategies for preserving dark and quiet skies. These strategies can be used by the International Astronomical Union’s Center for the Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky (D&QS), as well as other groups committed to preserving access to the cosmos from Earth and beyond.

This document provides a general overview of some of the topics that were up for discussion at the workshop, but is not meant to be definitive in scope. Moreover, the paper is informed by work from several different groups, including the Outer Space Institute and the International Astronomical Union’s Centre for Protection of the Dark and Quiet Sky Work Package 2 team.

We recognize that both astronomical observations and satellites bring great benefits to society. This is not an all-or-nothing issue. The challenge, rather, is to minimize the negative consequences of satellite systems, while still harnessing their benefits. Negative consequences range from orbital light and spectrum pollution to the de facto appropriation of orbits through orbital congestion and debris. The list of consequences is long and growing.

The challenge is all the more imposing because space is being developed much faster than national governments and regulatory agencies seem able to respond.

- Since the Dark and Quiet Skies II conference in the fall of 2021, the number of SpaceX Starlink satellites has more than doubled.
- Stratospheric aerosols have been confirmed to contain spacecraft reentry particulates, the levels of which are certain to grow—with unknown consequences.
- In the past several years, filings for radio spectrum for over one million satellites have been submitted to the International Telecommunication Union.
- While SpaceX has made some progress in brightness mitigation, it is also making larger satellites.
- BlueWalker3 and five BlueBirds are among the brightest objects in the sky, and other large satellites are planned.
- LOFAR has detected noise emission (i.e., additional to radio emissions) from Starlink satellites. Other observatories are now attempting similar measurements.
- Radio astronomical facilities cannot rely on terrestrial seclusion to avoid radiofrequency spectrum interference from satellites.

Another issue is that most people have lost access to a truly dark sky,¹ and with this, a connection with the cosmos. They do not know what they are missing and are unaware of the changes that have occurred and are ongoing.

1. General considerations

Throughout this discussion paper, we use “astronomical observations” (AOs) as a general term that is inclusive of all ways that people use the sky, including astronomy across the electromagnetic spectrum. It is further intended to include dark sky viewing, natural heritage, and cultural heritage. While most considerations here will be for ground-based astronomy, “astronomical observations” is a phrase that could also include space-based observations and, in principle, even observations from other bodies such as the Moon.

We urge the rejection of false dilemmas, such as having to choose between astronomy and satellites or between astronomy and fighting some grand challenge, such as climate change.² We also reject the notion that one activity is inherently good and another inherently bad – no group has, as a given, higher moral ground over another. At the same time, not all actions have equal or even similar impacts, and for this reason, distinctions between activities can and should be made. For example, observatories are not generating global pollution and changing the atmosphere in unprecedented ways.³

We emphasize these points because we are mindful not to present the idea that “satellites are bad” and “astronomy is good”. Indeed, we need only point to the Thirty Metre Telescope project on Maunakea, Hawai’i, to emphasize that astronomy can also cause harm, in this case, through continued actions of colonization. Nor do we engage in any sort of accounting game to determine which activity inherently provides the most “net” good. Rather, we are focused on orbital light and spectrum pollution itself and investigating mechanisms to prevent or at least reduce it.

2. Options on the table

In identifying and choosing strategies, it is important to consider the full range of possibilities. So far, companies have been encouraged to take voluntary mitigation measures and, to a lesser degree, to change spacecraft designs. Such voluntary measures could lead to new industry guidelines or best practices, though this does not appear to be happening yet. Militaries and

¹ See F Falchi et al, “The new world atlas of artificial night sky brightness”, *Science Advances*, 2(6), 2016: e1600377. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1600377>;

² This false dilemma was the starting point for a talk at the La Palma meeting, which laid out an ambitious plan to have a large, bright megaconstellation for observing cloud structures. As will be discussed, it will be essential to clearly and unequivocally reject such notions as we move forward.

³ Alteration of the atmosphere was predicted independently by two groups (Schulz and Glassmeier; Boley and Byers) and recently confirmed by measurements of aerosols (Murphy et al.): L. Schulz and K.-H. Glassmeier, “On the anthropogenic and natural injection of matter into Earth’s atmosphere”, *Advances in Space Research*, 67(3), 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2020.10.036>; A. Boley and M. Byers, “Satellite mega-constellations create risks in Low Earth Orbit, the atmosphere and on Earth”, *Scientific Report*, 11(10642), 2021, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-89909-7>; D. Murphy et al., “Metals from spacecraft reentry in stratospheric aerosol particles”, *PNAS*, 120(43), 2023, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2313374120>.

space and science agencies can also be encouraged to take voluntary mitigations measures and design their spacecraft with dark and quiet skies in mind.

However, voluntary measures, while fast and flexible, could be subject to change without notice, as we have seen with Starlink satellites, and new entrants could regard “best practices” as an unnecessary expense and therefore a barrier. This naturally leads us to the question of whether companies and government bodies should be compelled to behave in a certain way through law.

Legal arguments can matter in several different ways. Dispute settlement could be pursued within domestic courts, but also internationally, such as a request for an advisory opinion from the International Court of Justice. Legal arguments also matter for diplomacy, where the preference of states to act legally rather than illegally can usefully be engaged. Then there is public opinion, where legal arguments can help to generate a sense of legitimacy concerning state or corporate behaviour, or delegitimize and thus weaken the position of otherwise powerful actors. When assessing law-related options, the desired result should be kept in mind, rather than the development of legal arguments for argument’s sake.

Rules and regulations exist at multiple levels of governance,⁴ and can influence and strengthen one another across different levels. For example, national regulations could arise from domestic considerations, or from a state’s international obligations. International law is made and changed by states, with examples being treaties and customary international law.⁵ Non-state actors are sometimes able to influence this process, but are not themselves law-makers.

International rules adopted as a result of multilateral negotiations can help to provide a level playing field and prevent or reduce free-riding. Negotiations cannot anticipate every possible situation, so rules are designed with a degree of generality—enabling them to be interpreted and applied in new circumstances.

Negotiations and other diplomatic activities, as well as practice by states and non-state actors, can lead to guidelines and norms of behaviour. While non-binding “soft law” instruments and unwritten norms can have considerable influence on state actions, they can also be developed – albeit only with state consent – into binding treaty rules and customary international law. Orbital debris mitigation guidelines serve as an important reference: (1) for their success in being widely recognized and adopted and (2) for their failure in not keeping large debris out of Earth orbits (e.g., there are over 2000 abandoned rocket bodies in orbit).

Public engagement is a final and critically important tool. Media and members of the public can place considerable pressure on governments when motivated to do so. If part of a global movement, public engagement can further effect international change. With public engagement, to inform and to educate is one thing. But the truly difficult and necessary task is to *activate* the public into demanding that politicians protect dark and quiet skies. Activating the public is not

⁴ Rules at local levels of governance have played an important role in slowing the growth of light pollution and in some cases radio frequency spectrum pollution.

⁵ Customary International Law emerges as a result of a combination of (a) state practice and (b) *opinio juris*, i.e., an awareness that a state’s action is legally relevant. There is also a third source of international law through the “[T]he general principles of law recognized by the [community of nations]” (ICJ Article 38).

easy: the Cuyahoga River in Ohio literally caught fire a dozen times before the public demanded action. Once that occurred, local and national laws soon followed.⁶

3. Protection of dark and quiet skies should be discussed in multiple fora

With the different options above in mind, we focus first on possible diplomatic paths. One avenue, well known by those working on D&QS, is through the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS) and its subcommittees. D&QS advocates have been pushing for the creation of a new expert group under the COPUOS Science and Technical Subcommittee (COPUOS STSC). Although unsuccessful in 2023, the effort succeeded in 2024. UNESCO, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, has long concerned itself with outer space issues. As early as 1969, for instance, it hosted a meeting on the legal issues associated with space communications.⁷ UNESCO is also one of three partners (along with the Government of Italy and the International Atomic Energy Agency) operating the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics near Trieste. Much of UNESCO's early engagement on outer space was led by Frank Malina, the first director of the Jet Propulsion Lab at CalTech, who later worked for the international organization from 1947-1953.

One of the more promising avenues that the astronomical community might wish to pursue at UNESCO is the adoption of a “statement” by the organization. An example is the “Seville Statement on Violence”, first adopted by an international meeting of scientists convened by the Spanish National Commission for UNESCO in 1986 and then adopted by UNESCO at the twenty-fifth session of its General Conference in 1989. The statement was designed to refute “the notion that organized human violence is biologically determined”.⁸

Another possible avenue is the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP), which has led the adoption of highly effective multilateral treaties on chlorofluorocarbons (Vienna Convention on the Protection of the Ozone Layer and its Montreal Protocol),⁹ persistent organic pollutants (Stockholm Convention),¹⁰ and mercury (Minimata Convention).¹¹ UNEP is now working toward a multilateral treaty on plastic pollution, including in the marine environment.¹² Given the parallels between the ocean plastic crisis and the multiple crises associated with the proliferation of space objects (debris, atmospheric chemistry, climate impacts, light and radio

⁶ See L. Boissoneault, “The Cuyahoga River Caught Fire at Least a Dozen Times, but No One Cared Until 1969”, *Smithsonian Magazine*, 2019, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/cuyahoga-river-caught-fire-least-dozen-times-no-one-cared-until-1969-180972444/>

⁷ E. G. Lee, “UNESCO Meeting on Space Communications: Legal Issues”, *UT Law Journal*, 20(3), 1970, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/825226>

⁸ For background on the Seville Statement, see: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Seville_Statement_on_Violence .

⁹ United Nations, “Vienna Convention on for the Protection of the Ozone Layer”, Vienna, 22 March 1985; United Nations, “Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer”, Montreal, 16 September 1987; both available at <https://legal.un.org/avl/ha/vcpol/vcpol.html>.

¹⁰ United Nations, “Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants”, Stockholm 22 May 2001, <https://www.pops.int/>.

¹¹ United Nations, “Minimata Convention on Mercury”, Kumamoto, 10 October 2013, <https://minamataconvention.org/en>.

¹² United Nations, “Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee on Plastic Pollution”, UN Environmental Program, <https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution>.

interference with astronomy, impacts on wildlife, etc.), it may be possible to steer UNEP toward the protection of the Earth-space environment.

This is not an exhaustive list of possible avenues. We provide these options for consideration in their own right, and as examples of the possibilities that might emerge through a wider analysis of international institutions. To accomplish such an analysis, experts in international relations – including diplomats and former UN officials – will need to be included in further research and strategizing.

It should also be kept in mind that there are several possible outcomes from multilateral processes. One possibility, of course, is a binding treaty, as mentioned above. However, states may also choose to amend an existing treaty or add a protocol to it. Another possibility is a non-binding instrument, which could take the form of a declaration or set of guidelines. Non-binding instruments can still guide behaviour, as again has been the case with debris mitigation guidelines and planetary protection policies. One clear advantage of non-binding instruments is their *relative* ease of updating—a task that states may choose to delegate to a permanent working group or committee.¹³

Ultimately, states are responsible for implementing treaties through national laws and regulations, the content of which may also be informed by non-binding instruments.

States can always choose to move independently. This will often be the fastest route toward meaningful action, but it can also lead to mixed results, races to the bottom, and even flags of convenience. States will sometimes resist acting due to a perception that restrictions will cause them to “fall behind” other states. But this perception will sometimes be false. Indeed, a single state can take unilateral action that leads to rapid multilateral change, as we explained in a 2022 article:¹⁴

The 1970s saw a growing risk to oceans and coastlines from oil spills as well as efforts, nationally and internationally, to adopt a requirement for ‘double hulls’ on tankers. The shipping industry, concerned about increased costs, was able to stymie these efforts—until 1989, when the Exxon Valdez spilled roughly 11 million gallons of oil into Alaska’s Prince William Sound. Media coverage of the accident made the issue of oil spills a matter of public concern, and after the National Transportation Safety Board concluded that a double hull would have substantially reduced if not eliminated the spill, the US government required all new tankers calling at US ports to have double hulls. This unilateral move then prompted the International Maritime Organization to amend the International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL Convention) in 1992 to require double hulls on new tankers and, through further amendments in 2001 and 2003, to accelerate the retirement of single-hulled tankers.

We went on to note that “the 1992 amendments to the MARPOL Convention have since been ratified by 150 states (including the US, Liberia and Panama), representing 98% of the world’s shipping tonnage.”

¹³ Orbital debris once again provides an example, with the inter-agency debris coordination committee (IADC).

¹⁴ M. Byers, E. Wright, A. Boley, and C. Byers, *Nature Astronomy* 6, 1093-1097, 2022, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41550-022-01718-8>.

This example is particularly relevant to satellites as, like shipping vessels, they operate in an area beyond national jurisdiction and the pollution they cause affects states worldwide. However, the example is also cautionary—the rapid action initiated by states was prompted by a disaster, something that everyone will wish to avoid.

It is, perhaps, a desire to avoid disaster that opens up possible avenues for change. For example, acknowledgments of the need to avoid light pollution are being advanced by the UK’s Earth Space Sustainability Initiative.¹⁵ These are not done as a separate issue. Instead, they are being included within the broader “sustainability” package, including debris, atmospheric pollution, security, and casualty risks.

On the one hand, there is a danger that inclusion in a package will lead to inattention or even trade-offs, with some issues drawing the focus and efforts of states away from others. On the other hand, linking multiple sustainability challenges can highlight how solutions to one problem (e.g., drag sails for faster deorbiting) could spill over into other challenges (light pollution).¹⁶

Finally, decision-makers will often resist change unless there are political reasons for acting. For this reason, it is necessary that we educate the public and lead them into action—before even more “damage” is done to the sky.

4. Legal character of astronomical observations

Progress within the above fora could be heavily influenced by how astronomical observations (AOs) are perceived by lawmakers, diplomats, and the public. For this reason, one should ask whether AOs are a form of “exploration and use of outer space”—as protected by Article I of the Outer Space Treaty (OST).

This question may seem a bit odd, as AOs are unquestionably the primary way by which space is explored. It is indeed the most accessible way that people, including children, access outer space. The question that we ask, though, is not one that is conceptual or academic. Rather, we are interested in whether AOs are an “exploration and use” of outer space under the OST.

In our 2023 open access book,¹⁷ we provide a full treaty interpretation of “exploration and use” as it relates to astronomy. We conclude that AOs constitute “exploration and use” and that states parties to the OST have an obligation to show “due regard” toward states engaging in AOs (Article IX, OST). Said differently, actors should be coordinating with astronomy and other sky users not just because this is a “nice” or perhaps advantageous thing to do,¹⁸ but because the states that licence their satellites are required to do so.

¹⁵ Earth Space Sustainability Initiative, <https://www.essi.org/>.

¹⁶ Examples abound. One might instead imagine consequences for radio astronomy through satellite design, including widespread use of tethers.

¹⁷ M. Byers and A. Boley, “Who Owns Outer Space?”, Cambridge University Press, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108597135>. See also G. Rotola and A. Williams, “Regulatory Context of Conflicting Uses of Outer Space: Astronomy and Satellite Constellations”, *Air and Space Law*, 46(4/5), 2021, <https://doi.org/10.54648/aila2021031>. An early draft of the treaty interpretation by A. Boley and G. Rotola can be found in “Dark and Quiet Skies II Working Group Reports”, Chapter 2.2, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5874725>, which was greatly expanded upon and improved in Byers and Boley.

¹⁸ There could be an advantage for a company to work with astronomers should it be seen as positive for public relations reasons, or by attempting to dictate the extent of any guidelines or regulations that emerge.

5. International environmental law

While international law, including environmental principles, applies to space by virtue of Art. III OST, this does not mean all the rules automatically extend there. However, the adoption of environmentally oriented non-binding instruments such as the Long-term Sustainability Guidelines, the Space Debris Guidelines, and the Planetary Protection Policies all support the application of certain environmental principles to space.

International environmental law is centred on a global responsibility to safeguard the environment from harm, including in areas beyond national jurisdictions—with outer space being the quintessential area beyond national jurisdiction. Principle 21 of the 1972 Stockholm Declaration was the starting point: “States have, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations ... the responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause damage to the environment of other States or of *areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction*” (emphasis added).¹⁹ Many multilateral environmental treaties now include the obligation not to cause damage to the environment of other states or of areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction,²⁰ and the International Court of Justice has referred to this rule on numerous occasions.²¹

Principle 21 does not specify what constitutes “damage” but changes to the chemistry of the upper atmosphere are clearly within its scope. So, too, could light pollution from satellites, particularly given the damage caused to natural heritage, including nocturnal animals and migrating birds.

Principle 15 of the 1992 Rio Declaration²² established the precautionary principle: “In order to protect the environment, the precautionary approach shall be widely applied by States according to their capabilities. Where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation”.²³ Similarly, Article 3(3) of the 1992 UN Framework Convention on Climate Change reads, “Parties should take precautionary measures to anticipate,

¹⁹ “Declaration of the Nations Conference on the Human Environment”, A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1, 1972, <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972>

²⁰ See e.g. United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, 10 December 1982, 1833 UNTS 397 Art. 194(2) (entered into force 16 November 1994): ‘States shall take all measures necessary to ensure that activities under their jurisdiction or control are so conducted as not to cause damage by pollution to other States and their environment, and that pollution arising from incidents or activities under their jurisdiction or control does not spread beyond the areas where they exercise sovereign rights in accordance with this Convention’; Convention on Biological Diversity, 5 June 1992, 1760 UNTS 79 Art. 3 (entered into force 29 December 1993): ‘States have, in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations and the principles of international law, the sovereign right to exploit their own resources pursuant to their own environmental policies, and the responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause damage to the environment of other States or of areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction.’

²¹ See, e.g.: Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons, Advisory Opinion, [1996] ICJ Rep 226 at 241, para. 29; Case Concerning the Gabcikovo-Nagymaros Project (Hungary v. Slovakia), [1997] ICJ Rep 7 at 41, para. 53.

²² United Nations General Assembly, “Rio Declaration on Environment and Development”, A/CONF.151/26 (Vol. 1), https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/migration/generalassembly/docs/globalcompact/A_CONF.151_26_Vol.I_Declaration.pdf

²³ This principle calls into question decisions by regulatory bodies that provide approval actions under the premise of a lack of data, even if such data could be obtained.

prevent or minimize the causes of climate change and mitigate its adverse effects. Where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty should not be used as a reason for postponing such measures”.²⁴ Today, the precautionary principle is central to numerous treaties, including most recently the 2018 Central Arctic Ocean Fisheries Agreement to which the United States, Russia, China and the European Union are all parties.²⁵ This treaty prohibits all commercial fishing in the central Arctic Ocean until scientific research establishes that a sustainable fishery can take place.

The precautionary principle is now widely accepted as constituting customary international law.²⁶ It therefore binds all states with regard to their exploration and use of space, including activities licenced by them that are carried out by companies and other non-state actors.

With regard to megaconstellations and AOs, the most significant component of the precautionary principle is the now widely-recognized responsibility to conduct an environmental impact assessment prior to authorizing an activity that could cause damage to the environment of areas beyond the limits of national jurisdiction.²⁷ In the United States, the FCC failed to conduct an environmental impact assessment for Starlink before issuing a license for 12,000 satellites. That omission, in our assessment, violates both the Outer Space Treaty and customary international law. Other states, such as the United Kingdom when it licensed OneWeb’s megaconstellation, may have engaged in similar contraventions. To avoid ongoing and further violations of international law, the construction of these megaconstellations should be paused until environmental impact assessments can take place.

Although the existence of a legal requirement to pause the construction of megaconstellations might seem surprising to non-lawyers, ‘cessation’ is a well-established remedy in public international law. As Francesca Capone recently explained in the Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law:

The State responsible for the commission of a wrongful act is under an obligation to cease the conduct and to offer appropriate assurances, normally given verbally, and guarantees of non-repetition, such as preventive measures to be taken to avoid repetition of the breach. The function of cessation is twofold: to end the violation and protect the continuing validity and effectiveness of the primary rule. Thus, it safeguards both the rights of the State injured and the interests of the international community as a whole.²⁸

²⁴ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 9 May 1992, 1771 UNTS 107 Art. 3(3) (entered into force 21 March 1994).

²⁵ Agreement to Prevent Unregulated High Seas Fisheries in the Central Arctic Ocean, 3 October 2018, Can TS 2021 No (entered into force 25 June 2021).

²⁶ Patricia Birnie and Alan Boyle, *International Law and the Environment*, 2nd ed (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002) 120.

²⁷ See *Case Concerning Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay)*, [2010] ICJ Rep 14 at 79, para. 197; *Certain Activities Carried Out by Nicaragua in the Border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua)*, 2015 ICJ Rep 665 at 706, para. 104. See also Ulrich Beyerlin and Thilo Marauhn, *International Environmental Law* (Oxford: Hart, 2011) at 54.

²⁸ Francesca Capone, ‘Remedies’, in Anne Peters, ed, *Max Planck Encyclopedia of Public International Law* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, article last modified Oct 2020), online: opil.ouplaw.com/view/10.1093/law:epil/9780199231690/law-9780199231690-e1089.

All that being said, environmental impact assessments will not necessarily prevent a violation of international law. A government that conducted an environmental impact assessment and then licensed a megaconstellation in defiance of its findings would be contravening the obligation of due regard, as would one that conducted an environment impact assessment in a manner that was not objective or scientifically rigorous. A state negatively impacted by a megaconstellation (for instance, a state that hosted, operated, or otherwise supported AOs) would still be entitled to protest, make a claim, seek third-party dispute settlement or engage in countermeasures, just like any state suffering damage because of a violation of any other rule of international law.

The problem, again, is not an absence of international law but a limited number of options for international dispute settlement against the powerful states that are licensing megaconstellations. This leads us to suggest two possible avenues: an advisory opinion from the International Court of Justice; or invoking the Liability Convention.

6. Advisory Opinion from International Court of Justice

An advisory opinion is legal advice provided to the United Nations by the International Court of Justice, in accordance with Article 96 of the UN Charter. The UN General Assembly, which is made up of all 193 UN member states, may request advisory opinions on “any legal question”.²⁹

As an example, in 2023, a request for an advisory opinion was made by the General Assembly on the issue of climate change. Initiated by grassroots activists and championed by Vanuatu, it seeks the confirmation and clarification of relevant state obligations. The Vanuatu campaign provides an excellent model of how to take an issue, such as the threat posed to the sky and the environment by megaconstellations, to the advisory jurisdiction of the ICJ.³⁰

Although advisory opinions are not themselves binding on states, they carry weight as reasoned, authoritative assessments of the law by the most respected international court, and therefore have considerable moral authority.

Requests for advisory opinions are debated, voted on and adopted as UN General Assembly resolutions. Importantly, the General Assembly does not operate on the basis of consensus: All that is required is a simple majority of the UN member states present and voting. Abstentions do not count as votes. Thus, requests for advisory opinions do not require support by a majority of UN member states; they simply require more votes in favor than against.

A draft resolution can be proposed by just one state, though a group of states is more desirable. This is because a great deal of diplomacy takes place before the resolution is proposed, as well as when the resolution is being considered and debated. Ideally, proponents seek to build a coalition of like-minded states: some will champion the resolution; others will simply vote for it. Even states that can be persuaded to abstain rather than vote against the resolution could be considered allies in this process.

²⁹ Charter of the United Nations, Chapter XIV, Article 96, <https://legal.un.org/repertory/art96.shtml>.

³⁰ It is worth spending time on the campaign’s website: <https://www.vanuatuicj.com/>

Pursuing a request for an advisory opinion can accomplish several goals. It can generate media coverage and public understanding of the issue, thus changing the political landscape for national decision-makers. It may prompt multilateral negotiations on the issue. It could, depending on the outcome, further strengthen the arguments of astronomers when they engage with governments, the media, and industry.

That said, such an action must be taken carefully. The 1996 Advisory Opinion on Nuclear Weapons is an example of an outcome that disappointed its proponents. In a split vote, the ICJ was unable to conclude that the use of nuclear weapons is prohibited in all circumstances, as those behind the request for an advisory opinion had hoped.

The states that championed the proposal for a new expert group at COPUOS could be the logical ones to propose a D&QS draft resolution: Chile, Spain, Slovakia, Bulgaria, the Dominican Republic, Peru, and South Africa. South Africa may be in a particularly strong position to champion the proposal given its central role in the Square Kilometer Array Observatory.

With this option now in mind, we advise against seeking an advisory opinion at the present moment. It is important that the new D&QS expert group at COPUOS has time to function. Since COPUOS is a committee of the UN General Assembly, member states will want to see whether the expert group makes any progress – before supporting a change of venue to the ICJ.

7. Liability Convention

Another path to dispute settlement could involve a state that owns a major ground-based observatory invoking the 1972 Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects (Liability Convention) against a state that licenses a megaconstellation because of Article II, which reads: “A launching State shall be absolutely liable to pay compensation for damage caused by its space object on the surface of the earth or to aircraft in flight”. Absolute liability means that the state claiming damage does not need to establish the existence of fault; indeed, the only legal issue is whether light and spectrum pollution are causing “damage”.

“Damage” is defined in Article I(1) of the Liability Convention as meaning “loss of life, personal injury or other impairment of health; or loss of or damage to property of States or of persons, natural or juridical, or property of international intergovernmental organisations.” Clearly, physical damage to an observatory or to its personnel, such as from re-entry debris, is covered. But what about loss of data or damage to Earth-based sensors? Answering this question requires a systematic treaty interpretation in accordance with the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties, the provisions of which are widely accepted as codifying customary international law.

Article 31(1) of the Vienna Convention specifies: “A treaty shall be interpreted in good faith in accordance with the ordinary meaning to be given to the terms of the treaty in their context and in the light of its object and purpose”. We start with ordinary meaning: According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, one definition of “property” is “something owned or possessed”. Data can be owned, but are data included within the ordinary meaning of “property”? In the 21st century, where large sectors of the economy are digitized, the answer is clearly “yes”. As for

Earth-based sensors, these are tangible objects that are bought and sold. Again, these are clearly property within the ordinary meaning of the term.

We now look to context and the object and purposes of the treaty, where passages of the preamble to the Liability Convention point toward a broad interpretation of “damage”. For example, “Recognizing the need to elaborate effective international rules and procedures concerning liability for damage caused by space objects and to ensure, in particular, the prompt payment under the terms of this Convention of a full and equitable measure of compensation to victims of such damage” and “Believing that the establishment of such rules and procedures will contribute to the strengthening of international co-operation in the field of the exploration and use of outer space for peaceful purposes, ...”. These provisions clearly indicate an intention to ensure compensation for all harm caused to other states as a result of the operation of spacecraft.

As part of a Vienna Convention treaty interpretation, we also need to consider “any subsequent practice in the application of the treaty which establishes the agreement of the parties regarding its interpretation”. In this case, there is just one instance of subsequent practice: In 1978, a Soviet surveillance satellite malfunctioned, re-entered the atmosphere in an uncontrolled manner and spread radioactive material over 120,000 square kilometres of northern Canada. Canada presented a claim of CAD \$6 million for the cleanup costs, under the Liability Convention. After three rounds of negotiations, the Soviet Union, while not admitting liability, agreed to pay half that amount “in full and final settlement of all matters connected with the disintegration of the Soviet satellite Cosmos-954”.³¹ Obviously, the cleanup costs involved economic rather than physical “damage”, making this one case of subsequent practice a clear indicator toward a broad interpretation of that term.

A claim under the Liability Convention is unlikely to lead to a binding decision. For while a Claim Commission will be established, as per the treaty, its decision will only “be final and binding if the parties have so agreed; otherwise the Commission shall render a final and recommendatory award, which the parties shall consider in good faith.” But the final decision, with reasons, will be made public and could carry considerable legitimacy and therefore political and ethical weight.

Even if the Commission ruled that “damage” under the Liability Convention had to be read narrowly, the facts that a complaint has been made and a Claims Commission established are likely to attract considerable attention—helping to educate the public about the issue.

A more likely cause of a negative ruling is that the Liability Convention places a limit of one year from the time that the “damage” was recognized to make a claim. This reflects, in part, a view in the Liability Convention of dealing with discrete events rather than injury related to a relentlessly growing form of damage. And it is possible that a Claims Commission would waive that limit for the latter kind of damage, perhaps choosing to focus instead on threshold events. For example, when the Square Kilometre Array Observatory comes fully online, it may notice an

³¹ “Protocol between the Government of Canada and the Government of the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics”, 2 April 1981, https://www.jaxa.jp/library/space_law/chapter_3/3-2-2-1_e.html; see also G. Zhukov and O. Volynskaya, “Current Problems of International Responsibility and Liability in the Domain of Space Activities”, *Moscow Journal of International Law*, 3, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.24833/0869-0049-2013-3-92-103>.

intolerable amount of data loss in terms of operations. Such an event could compel SKAO member states to trigger the Liability Convention, and it would seem reasonable for a Claim Commission to hear their claim.

Making a claim under the Liability Convention is thus a real option for states that own major observatories. However, the probability of a legal “win” is not particularly high. Nor will a claim under the Liability Convention attract as much media and public attention as, say, a request for an advisory opinion at the ICJ. It is thus, perhaps, a mechanism that could be used following an ICJ advisory opinion, should it be needed.

8. International Telecommunication Union

The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) is the multilateral body responsible for radiofrequency spectrum allocation, concerning itself with wavelengths of light longer than 1000 microns (300 GHz). Optical and infrared light are outside its current scope; however, the ITU could indirectly become involved in both “dark” and “quiet” skies, for instance through orbit allocations or while addressing broader space sustainability issues.

Founded in 1865 as the International Telegraph Union, the ITU has, since 1947, been a specialized agency of the United Nations with a legal structure composed of the ITU Constitution, the ITU Convention, and its administrative regulations. The corresponding radio regulations (RRs) are of course relevant to quiet skies directly, and require ITU member states to register their satellites at the ITU and to coordinate frequency use with other actors. It is within the RRs that radio astronomy has “protected” bands.³²

An important feature of the ITU is that, while member states are bound to both the constitution and the administrative regulations, they are able to update the RRs at ITU World Radio Conferences, held every three to four years, and thus can address new developments with binding rules. For this reason, the ITU with its 193 Member states is a relatively effective, widely accepted international rule-making body.

Historically, the ITU has only regulated orbital “slots” for satellites in geostationary orbit (GEO), situated roughly 35,800 km above Earth. However, the fast-rising launch rate of satellites into Low Earth Orbit (LEO), below an altitude of 2,000 km, introduces new opportunities and challenges.

The ITU Constitution and RRs establish that the radiofrequency spectrum is a finite resource that must be used efficiently and shared equitably. In recent years, filings for satellite megaconstellations have presented a series of challenges to this. Some of the challenges include large, frequent, and speculative filings for radiofrequency spectrum rights,³³ often involving

³² Regions of the radiofrequency spectrum (bands) that are protected for use by astronomy are a small fraction of the regulated spectrum, although those bands have very strict non-interference requirements. Radio astronomy has maintained access to other parts of the spectrum through, in large part, physical isolation. Satellite interference increasingly precludes that option for the relevant bands.

³³ C. Henry, “ITU wants megaconstellations to meet tougher launch milestones”, Space News, 2019, <https://spacenews.com/itu-wants-megaconstellations-to-meet-tougher-launch-milestones/>

many thousands of satellites.³⁴ Member states have already sought to address the issue of satellite megaconstellations through the introduction of milestone requirements,³⁵ although so far this has not deterred large filings and possible “spectrum warehousing”.³⁶

The ITU is aware of the many challenges associated with the proliferation of satellites, particularly megaconstellations. The 2023 World Radio Conference (WRC-23) included discussions on this topic. Moreover, the ITU Radiocommunication Sector (ITU-R) Working Groups have explored ways to better model and determine power levels produced collectively by large non-GEO satellite constellations that cause interference to other satellite systems, with implications for radio astronomy.

8.1. Expand the mandate of the ITU

There are several ways in which the ITU could help to mitigate orbital light pollution. First, the member states of the ITU could, in principle, expand its mandate. The ITU’s mandate has been expanded before and could be expanded again. Again, the organization was created in 1865 as the International Telegraph Union. In 1932, the ITU changed its name (but not its acronym) to the International Telecommunication Union to reflect its expanded responsibilities over radio and telephone communications. In 1947, it undertook a major expansion of the Table of Frequency Allocations. However, expanding the mandate to deal with light pollution is a big ask for an organization that is currently struggling to deal with the demand for radio spectrum for satellites, not to mention the ongoing expansion in mobile communications on Earth’s surface.

8.2. Make changes within the existing mandate of the ITU

Another option is to make changes to the RRs or introduce new recommendations that could have an indirect but positive effect on orbital light pollution, such as by improving the equitable use of the radiofrequency spectrum. For example, the noted milestone requirements could, if stringently applied over the longer term, reduce the number of megaconstellations on orbit. In a WRC Agenda, a proposal to limit the tolerated deviations in the filed parameters for satellite systems could again indirectly mitigate orbital light pollution by preventing satellites from relocating to or loitering in orbits where they are brighter. Such indirect approaches are clearly within the ITU’s mandate and are relatively easy steps to take.

³⁴ J. Foust, “Satellite operators criticize ‘extreme’ megaconstellation filings”, Space News, 2021, <https://spacenews.com/satellite-operators-criticize-extreme-megaconstellation-filings/>

³⁵ ITU, Resolution 35, <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/space/Pages/res35main.aspx>

³⁶ A. Falle et al., “One million (paper) satellites”, Science, 382(6667), 2023, <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.adi4639>

8.3. ITU could play a more direct role in managing orbital slots

A third option is for the ITU to play a more direct role in managing orbital slots. The organization already explicitly acknowledges that both orbits and the radiofrequency spectrum are scarce resources. Article 44.2 of the ITU Convention states: “In using frequency bands for radio services, Member States shall bear in mind that radio frequencies and any associated orbits, including the geostationary-satellite orbit, are limited natural resources and that they must be used rationally, efficiently and economically, in conformity with the provisions of the Radio Regulations, so that countries or groups of countries may have equitable access to those orbits and frequencies, taking into account the special needs of the developing countries and the geographical situation of particular countries.”

The ITU’s role in radiofrequency management extends to all orbits, but so far, only GEO has seen the ITU ensure coordination of satellite positions among member states. GEO holds the unique attribute that satellites there remain in a “fixed” position relative to a point on the Earth’s surface. This synchronous positioning is invaluable for some kinds of communications satellites, as it provides consistent and uninterrupted coverage to a particular geographical area. Recognizing the scarcity and high demand of GEO, the ITU regulates the spatial position of GEO satellites and ensures coordination among member states. The ITU also requires filing of orbital parameters for non-GEO satellites but has not yet, through its member states, shown any willingness to regulate their spatial distribution.

It is not obvious what that regulation would look like, as the positions of non-GEO satellites relative to the Earth are continuously changing. However, parameters such as inclination, eccentricity, and altitude can still be used to understand any state’s contribution to orbital densities at various altitudes. Again, determining what constitutes equitable use is a challenge, but ensuring that no-one appropriates an entire orbit through de facto occupation is not just a necessity, it may even be legally required.

Article II of the OST stipulates that “Outer space, including the moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means.” As already discussed in previous sections, Article VI of the OST makes states responsible for their national actors. Thus, if a state or non-state actor were to occupy or use a region of orbital space to such an extent that no one else can use it, then they would seem to have contravened Article II.

Inevitably, though, one realizes a potential contradiction: By its very nature, the use of any given GEO slot precludes other states from using that slot. The difference is, ITU member states have clear agreements on how to coordinate and use GEO equitably. There is no equivalent for non-GEO satellite constellations. Yet states exploiting that lack of effective governance would again seem to be in violation of Article II of the OST. In any event, the ITU could play an important role in promoting a more equitable use of Earth orbits, by establishing clearer rules for non-GEO satellite slotting. And by doing so, it would help to address the challenge of light pollution.

8.4. Non-governmental experts could involve themselves in ITU study groups

There is one final possible path toward protecting dark and quiet skies. The ITU-R, the ITU’s Telecommunication Standardization Sector (ITU-T), and the ITU’s Telecommunication Development Sector (ITU-D) use study groups to “develop the technical bases for decisions taken at the World Radiocommunication Conferences and develop global standards (Recommendations), Reports and Handbooks on radiocommunication matters”,³⁷ and to develop “international standards... which act as defining elements in the global infrastructure of information and communication technologies”.³⁸ These study groups are open to experts worldwide, including academic and non-governmental organizations. Thus, astronomical organizations or even individual researchers can participate in them.

Private communications with ITU officials have indicated that there is some desire to incorporate space sustainability issues, broadly defined, into ITU study groups. If this is done, orbital light pollution could be included in the questions considered by the study groups or as part of a space sustainability package. We do note, however, that this particular path toward change could be long, time-consuming, and uncertain in its outcomes.

Final Thoughts

The unchecked proliferation of satellite systems, especially megaconstellations, is creating multiple grand challenges to the Earth-space environment, as well as the continued exploration and use of outer space. Here, we focused on just one of those grand challenges: light and spectrum pollution and their corresponding disruptions to astronomy and astronomical observations.

International law, including international space law and international environmental law, already include obligations that – when interpreted and applied in this new context – require states to mitigate light and spectrum pollution. This creates normative points of leverage for astronomers as they pursue community action, encourage state-to-state diplomacy, and engage multiple bodies at the United Nations.³⁹ Some of these steps can be taken in parallel, while others, such as an advisory opinion at the International Court of Justice, should only be pursued after other paths have been explored.

³⁷ ITU, Radiocommunications Study Groups, <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/study-groups/Pages/default.aspx>

³⁸ ITU, ITU-T in brief, <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/about/Pages/default.aspx>

³⁹ During the Astro-Sat Workshop, participants brainstormed a series of “action items” to expand on the possible options for astronomers. Those action items are available as a companion document to this one at https://outerspaceinstitute.ca/osisite/wp-content/uploads/Action_Item_Paragraphs_OSI_Workshop_Orbital_Light_Spectrum_Pollution_FINAL-U1.pdf